

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D7.6

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Summary:

This document describes the type of data collected in the CRM-geothermal project and how the data is curated. It also elaborates on the relations to IPR requirements and exploitation strategies. All data from the project shall be deposited in research data repositories according to the FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship such that it is possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user.

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Funded by
the European Union

Title:	Data Management Plan		
Lead beneficiary:	GFZ		
Other beneficiaries:	all		
Due date:	31 Oct 2022		
Nature:	Public		
Diffusion:	All partners, EC and general public		
Status:	Draft		
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.7268832		
License information:	CC-BY-4.0		
Recommended Citation:	Katrin Kieling, The Horizon Europe CRM-geothermal project: Deliverable 7.6 – Data Management Plan, Zenodo, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7268832		
Related Data:			
ORCID:	Katrin Kieling - ORCID: 0000-0003-0182-5090		
Document code:	CRM-GEOTHERMAL_D7.6		
Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 01	KK	24.10.2022	First draft submitted to partners
Version 02	KK	31.10.2022	Inclusion of comments by LL

Approval status				
	Name	Function	Date	Signature
Deliverable responsible	Katrin Kieling	Project manager	31.10.2022	
Reviewer	Luis Lopes	Partner LPRC	24.10.2022	
Project Coordinator	Katrin Kieling	Project Manager	31.10.2022	

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Data Management Plan (DMP) sets the framework for the handling of data produced in the Horizon Europe project CRM-geothermal. This includes the curation and archiving, and shall thereby assure the implementation of best practice procedures for data management during and beyond the lifetime of the project.

This data management plan describes the data that will be authored and how the data will be managed and made openly accessible. The content of the data management plan includes

- the types of data to be managed;
- provisions for archiving and long-term preservation,
- access policies and provisions; and
- the relations to IPR requirements and exploitation strategies.

In general, data from the project shall be deposited in a research data repository according to the FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al., 2016) such that it is possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate them – free of charge for any user.

In some cases, where the data is confidential, it is permitted to keep the data closed, following relevant provisions made in the Consortium Agreement or share it with restrictions. Appropriate justifications and reasoning must be provided for any data which will not be openly accessible.

This DMP is not a fixed document; it may evolve and be updated during the lifetime of CRM-geothermal.

2 INTRODUCTION

CRM-geothermal is project that is funded within the European Research and Innovation programme Horizon Europe. Consequently, the project complies with the obligations concerning the dissemination of results as described in Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement:

The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and by taking all of the following actions:

- *establish a data management plan (DMP) and regularly update it*
- *as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository;*
- *as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:*
 - *be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or*
 - *be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP*
- *provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data*

Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

In agreement with Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement "Open science: research data management", the CRM-geothermal beneficiaries will deposit the data resulting from the project in open access repositories. They will take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate, free of charge any underlying data (data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications) incl. metadata.

CRM-geothermal beneficiaries agree to make data available according to the FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al. (2016):

- Findable
e. g. DOI and metadata should be available
- Accessible
e. g. in an open access repository, in machine readable form
- Interoperable
e. g. through the use of standards, standard vocabularies
- Re-use
e. g. an appropriate license has to be assigned and embargo times for sensitive data need to be clarified

Providing access to the underlying data for each project deliverable will maximise the impact of the CRM-geothermal project. On the one hand, data can be re-used by third parties to accelerate their own research, on the other hand, visibility of the CRM-geothermal project as well as individual project partners is increased.

3 TYPES OF DATA

CRM-geothermal will produce different types of data, which can be divided into six main groups

1. Measured data
 - a. Data from analysis of fluids collected from geothermal sites
 - b. Data from experiments with synthetic fluids or with natural fluids, either in the laboratories or at pilot sites
 - c. Data from analysis of solids (e.g. scales) from geothermal sites or produced in lab experiments
2. Synthetic data (i.e. Modelled data and predictive models)
3. Data on geothermal fluids and associated metadata for the Fluid Atlas provided by third parties
 - a. Collected data from literature
 - b. Data provided by the operators of geothermal sites
4. Software / codes / models
5. Data used for the positioning the combined extraction of CRM and energy for communities and consumers
 - a. Interviews and consultations
 - b. Data from surveys
6. Data used for the positioning the combined extraction of CRM and energy for investors and policymakers (Current supply of CRM, their market prices, the CAPEX and OPEX of mining operations, the potentially extracted CRM quantities, the cost of combined extraction compared to traditional mining, and the estimated evolution of the demand/supply)
 - a. Data collected from literature review
 - b. Data collected from CRM-geothermal partners

These diverse datasets, originating from different experimental procedures, chemical analyses, numerical simulations, or surveys and questionnaires will have various file formats and metadata associated with them.

3.1 MEASURED DATA

3.1.1 Data from analysis of fluids collected from geothermal sites

CRM-geothermal partners will collect data and fluid samples from various geothermal sites and analyse those fluids. Such data including associated metadata will include;

- Site specific information (e.g. P, T, flowrate)
- chemical compositions of fluids (e.g. major and trace elements, gas content) determined by different analytical techniques;

- model data based on lab results (such as the characterization of kinetic laws, or solubility measurements in relation with the lab data acquired by project partners)

3.1.2 Data from experiments with synthetic fluids or with natural fluids, either in the laboratories or at pilot sites

During the CRM-geothermal project, several experiments will be performed with synthetic fluids or natural fluids and targeted extraction process.

- Adsorptive extraction by ion sieves
- Extraction via selective ion exchange membranes
- Adsorption by means of modified (bio-)polymers
- Bioextraction
- Helium extraction via membrane technology
- Gas diffusion electro-crystallisation (GDEx)

All of these experiments will measure the performance of the extraction processes for different elements, at different boundary conditions (temperature, pressure, chemical composition of the fluid), and with different processing times or different flow rates. This will also include the energy consumption and material use for the extraction.

The resulting data will be mostly pointwise data in tables, time series, photos and drawings.

3.1.3 Data from analysis of solids (e.g. scales) from geothermal sites or produced in lab experiments

CRM-geothermal will investigate solid rocks, e.g. cores or cuttings from geothermal wells or rocks from outcrops of relevant formations, as well as precipitates (known as scalings) from geothermal installations or surface manifestations.

- Solid analyses will produce high resolution photographs and summary files
- Solid analysis will also include data on chemical compositions and partly contain mineralogical information

The resulting data will be mostly pointwise data in tables and photos.

3.2 SYNTHETIC DATA

Synthetic data produced within CRM-geothermal will be the results of numerical simulations:

- numerical calculations to determine and reproduce the experimental results obtained at the lab scale on synthetic fluids
- the chemical behaviour of the fluid in the geothermal fluid loop including chemical processes such as quantity and nature of precipitated minerals.

For publication of the results from the numerical simulations, the publication of input data is equally important as the resulting data, in order to be able to reproduce the results. Therefore, publication of model input and model output should go hand in hand.

3.3 DATA ON GEOTHERMAL FLUIDS AND ASSOCIATED METADATA FOR THE FLUID ATLAS

Data for the Fluid Atlas will be mostly in tabular form. Main data include the geology and the depth range of the specific site and the physical and chemical properties of the geothermal fluid. The

template for the data collection for the Fluid Atlas will build on experience from the REFLECT project and include improvements. All data will be collected in tabular form.

In the course of the project, it is planned to build a platform for online submission of additional data, which allows more detailed quality and plausibility checks of the inputs and will improve standardised inputs.

The data for the Fluid Atlas will be collected in a database which will form the basis for the presentation in an online GIS-tool, allowing the visualisation and querying of the dataset.

The data for the Fluid Atlas is obtained from three different sources:

- Collected data from literature
- Data obtained from analysis of fluids during the project lifetime
- Data provided by operators

CRM-geothermal will encourage operators to provide for their sites the relevant data. However, operators do not need to provide sensible or confidential data for publication. The CRM-geothermal consortium establishes an agreement with the operators of the geothermal sites from which fluid samples are taken and investigated in the course of the project. These agreements clarify that data which is generated by the analysis of fluid samples within CRM-geothermal should be published, at least in an anonymous form or after a certain embargo time.

3.4 SOFTWARE / CODES / MODELS

For modelling and simulation, CRM-geothermal partners will mostly use self-developed and open source software (WP2: MeshIt, GOLEM, PHREEQC, Watch, GEMS, WP1: Grafana, Prometheus, Python or Go-based data analytics), which is partly already available on the GitHub repository. All further software developments within the project will be openly available for reproduction of results and re-use of code.

3.5 DATA USED FOR THE POSITIONING THE COMBINED EXTRACTION OF CRM AND ENERGY FOR COMMUNITIES AND CONSUMERS

Within Task 4.2 of CRM-geothermal, for the pilot sites, there are three types of data that will be collected for the positioning the combined extraction of CRM and energy for communities and consumers:

- Interviews and consultations
- Data from surveys
- Data obtained from literature study

Within Task 4.4. CRM-geothermal partners will mainly use desk research, foresight exercises with experts and internal & external experts' inputs to draft the roadmap for market deployment. The data will be the replies/answers/contributions by experts as well as associated statistics and the description of the exercises.

All data collected from stakeholders and experts will be treated as anonymous as possible and all published data will be anonymised. The participants will be informed about the purpose of the data collection prior to the surveys and interviews and their written consent will be collected.

3.6 DATA USED FOR THE POSITIONING THE COMBINED EXTRACTION OF CRM AND ENERGY FOR INVESTORS AND POLICYMAKERS

CRM-geothermal partners will collect information on the current supply of CRM, their market prices, the CAPEX and OPEX of mining operations, the potentially extracted CRM quantities, the cost of combined extraction compared to traditional mining, and the estimated evolution of the demand/supply. This will include:

- Data collected from literature review and desktop studies
- Data collected from CRM-geothermal partners (see above, e.g. Measured data)

The data will be mostly in form pointwise data in tables, text and summaries.

4 DATA CURATION AND ARCHIVING

As guaranteed in the CRM-geothermal Grant Agreement, GFZ will provide the possibility to make data accessible via GFZ data services for all CRM-geothermal partners. But, since GFZ data service is limited to geoscientific data, it might not be the optimal repository for data related to the economic, social and governance research included in CRM-geothermal.

Therefore, CRM-geothermal has opened a community on Zenodo, which is broader and able to cover all aspects of the project. The Zenodo community is named “CRM-geothermal project” and accessible via the URL <https://zenodo.org/communities/crm-geothermal/>. The community will be curated by the CRM-geothermal project manager. Project partners can choose to assign their data publication to multiple communities, e.g. additionally to “CRM-geothermal project” also choose the “Deep geothermal” community or the community on EC-funded research <https://zenodo.org/communities/ecfunded>.

However, partners can also choose to archive their data in other repositories, as long as the repository ensures that the data is provided in a FAIR way on a long-term basis.

The data repositories that will be used by CRM-geothermal partners are listed in Table 1.

All datasets will be accompanied by rich metadata (adhering to DataCite metadata standard) to ensure that all datasets are findable. In addition, to further aid their discoverability, keywords describing the datasets will be added.

A short report describing the metadata and methods used to generate the data will be connected to each dataset. The dataset itself will receive a DOI and a Creative Commons license. The CRM-geothermal management team recommends a CC-BY-4.0 license, but more restrictive licences can of course be used if necessary.

Table 1: List of data repositories used by CRM-geothermal partners.

Repository	URL	Beneficiaries using	Specifically for one data type
GFZ data services	https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/portal/	GFZ, open to all CRM-geothermal partners	Geoscientific data
National Geoscience Data Centre (NGDC)	https://www.bgs.ac.uk/geological-data/national-geoscience-data-centre/	BGS/UKRI	Geoscientific data

GenBank	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/	UNINE	DNA sequences
Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures	https://www.dsmz.de/	UNINE	Strains (microbiology)
Swiss Culture Collection	https://ccos.ch/	UNINE	Strains (microbiology)
ENA	http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena	UNINE	Genomic data
EMDB	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe/emdb/	UNINE	Microscopy images
NCBI SRA	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra	UNINE	Metagenomics data
Server of UNIM available through a frontend at the website of the Institute of Environmental Management	https://www.hidrotanszek.hu/EN	UNIM, EFG	Fluid atlas
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/ - CRM-geothermal community - deep geothermal community - molecular_biology community	All partners	All types of data
Github	https://github.com/	INLECOM, GFZ	Code and tutorials

In general, we encourage CRM-geothermal partners to publish their data in separate data publication in the data repositories mentioned above. However, it is in principle possible to publish data related to a certain publication in the appendix of that publication, as long as the FAIR principles are still respected.

4.1 DATA ASSOCIATED TO PROJECT DELIVERABLES

All CRM-geothermal deliverables with the dissemination level “public” will be published in an open access repository. For each deliverable a DOI will be registered. In order to provide sufficient time for review, deliverables should be submitted to the coordination team three weeks before the deadline.

CRM-geothermal data and deliverables will have a clear copyright statement. The CRM-geothermal management recommends to use a CC-BY-4.0 license, but beneficiaries may choose more restrictive open access licences in order to protect their IPR.

Associated data should be indicated in the project deliverables and in other publications which are based on REFLECT data. Data should be deposited in the data repository before the submission of the deliverable or publication, such that data citation (including the DOI) can be properly included.

Associated data should be indicated in the project deliverables and in other publications which are based on CRM-geothermal data. Data should be deposited in the data repository before the submission of the deliverable or publication, such that data citation (including the DOI) can be properly included.

Table 2: Extract from CRM-geothermal deliverable template. DOI, License information, recommended citation, and associated data should be clearly indicated in the document.

Title:	Title of the document (for deliverables, please refer to the official document title indicated in the Grant Agreement)
Lead beneficiary:	The PP that manages the document preparation
Other beneficiaries:	Other PP the document is prepared for
Due date:	Date in which the document is to be issued
Nature:	Confidential/Public
Diffusion:	e.g. all Partners, WP-partners
Status:	Draft / Working Document / Final
Document code:	
DOI:	
License information:	
Recommended citation:	
Associated data:	

5 RELATIONS TO IPR REQUIREMENTS AND EXPLOITATION STRATEGIES

The approach of the European Commission with regard to data publication within Horizon Europe can be described as “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

In some cases, where the data is confidential, it is permitted to keep the data closed, following relevant provisions made in the Consortium Agreement or share it with restrictions. Appropriate justifications and reasoning must be provided for any data which will not be openly accessible.

If CRM-geothermal beneficiaries cannot obtain the permission from the operator or owner of a geothermal site to publish the data from their site, beneficiaries might need to opt-out from publishing the related data or metadata. In this case, the CRM-geothermal beneficiaries will try to anonymise or abstract the information gathered from these sites such that overarching conclusions can be drawn and made available.

Access to data may also be restricted for data which is sensitive because the research results might be economically exploitable. CRM-geothermal partners might need to opt-out from publishing, if a commercial exploitation is considered. However, in that case a specific exploitation plan for the results obtained during the project should be established, such that the project can show the economic exploitation strategy towards the funding agency.

6 GDPR

As of May 2018, the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) replaced the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC. GDPR has been designed to harmonise data privacy laws across Europe and to reshape the way organisations across the world approach data privacy. In CRM-geothermal, this concerns especially:

- Web contact forms and email subscriptions where personal data is requested and submitted by the user;
- Cookies and online tracking including on Social Media;
- Event registrations;
- Stakeholder interviews;
- Online surveys.

The collection of data will only be undertaken, if there's an explicit authorisation by data subjects, obtained by an informed consent procedure, that will be in place in all events/interviews/workshops with external participants. The request for consent will be given in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and understandable language, also detailing the purpose of data collection and treatment.

7 REFERENCES

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al.: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18, 2016